

ISic3635

I.Sicily inscription 3635

Language

Latin

Type**Material**

breccia (local)

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2006.04

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

Found in the pavement of the church of S. Giuseppe

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, S. Marco d'Alunzio, Museo della cultura e
delle Arti Figurative Bizantine e Normanne

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491407

EDCS 23900188

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2001.1109

Bonanno, C. 1997-1998. Scavi e indagini nel territorio di Caronia e San Marco d'Alunzio. *Kokalos*. 43-44: 423-451. At 448 tav.107.3

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